

ACTION OF SULPHUR MONOCHLORIDE AND SULPHUR DICHLORIDE ON NAPHTHALENE DERIVATIVES AND ON ANTHRACENE

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As a result of the interaction between sulphur mono- and dichlorides on the one hand and naphthalene derivatives and anthracene on the other, naphthalene dithiochloride, anthracene tetrathiochloride, 4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide are prepared. In the same manner thio compounds of α - and β -naphthylamines are obtained, which have been assigned provisional structures.

Although the action of chlorides and oxychlorides of sulphur on aliphatic and benzene derivatives has been studied by various workers (Lorand, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1927, 19, 733; Gurthie, *Quart. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1860, 12, 116; Smythe and Forster *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1195; Cohen and Skirrow, *ibid.*, 1879 75, 867; Naik, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1166; Schmidt, *Ber.* 1878, 11, 1169; Coffey, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1921, 40, 747; Ray, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1956), little work appears to have been done on anthracene, and naphthalene derivatives. Therefore a systematic study of these compounds containing -OH, -CO₂H, -COCH₃, -OCOCH₃ and NH₂ groups as substituents in the naphthalene ring was undertaken and the results are now reported in this paper.

Anthracene reacts with both sulphur monochloride and sulphur dichloride in presence of aluminium-mercury couple, to give anthracene-9:10-tetrathio dichloride, m.p. 257°. In the absence of a catalyst, however, anthracene and sulphur monochloride gave only anthracene-9-dithiochloride in conformity with the experiments of Lippmann and Pollak (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2767) and contrary to those of Friedländer and Simon (*Ber.*, 1922, 58, 3969).

α -Naphthol reacts violently with sulphur dichloride but with sulphur monochloride it gives 4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl disulphide, m. p. 212° in small yields (cf Airan and Shah, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1940, 9, iii, 120, 125; 1942, 10 v, 129). On treatment with sulphuryl chloride the latter produced 4-chloro- α -naphthol, m. p. 116-17° as an evidence of the structure assigned above. 2:2'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide was obtained with β -naphthol and sulphur chlorides, but with the monochloride, in addition, a trisulphide, m. p. 118° (substitution in 4 position) instead of the tetrasulphide as reported by Henrique (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2993) was obtained. The presence of hydroxyl groups in these compounds has been proved by acetylation and estimation of acetyl groups and the position of substitution of the sulphur residues, by bromination and also by treating with diazobenzene chloride. 2-Acetyl- α -naphthol gives with sulphur

dichloride, a monosulphide as well as a disulphide, the latter being produced when some alcohol is present in ether used for the reaction. In addition, a trisulphide could also be obtained (*cf.* Airan and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

1:2- and 2:3-Hydroxynaphthoic acids give only monosulphides but α - and β -acetoxynaphthalenes fail to react with the sulphur chlorides. α - and β -Naphthylamines react with sulphur monochloride and sulphur dichloride to yield two trisulphidic hydrochlorides, m. p. 210° and 115°, respectively. On treatment with sodium hydroxide, the free bases, m. p. 195° and 150°, unchanged by treatment with acetic anhydride, are obtained. Formulae (I) and (II) are provisionally assigned to these compounds (*cf.* Jacobson, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1897; Hoffmann, *ibid.*, p. 1798).

The formation of mono-, di- and trisulphides in the above reactions, can be easily explained on the basis of the following equations studied by various workers (Richter, *Ber.*, 1917, 49, 1024; Marchand, *Annalen*, 1841, 40, 233); Lowry, McHatton and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 746).

The rapid inter-conversions of these compounds *in situ* appear to be responsible for the formation of the different types of the reaction products. It may also be pointed out in this connection that (i) the presence of catalysts like aluminium-mercury couple facilitates introduction of two -S₂Cl groups in anthracene; (ii) hydroxy groups (*cf.* naphthols) activate the naphthalene nucleus with respect to the action of sulphur chlorides; (iii) additional presence of CO₂H and COCH₃ groups has some modifying effect; (iv) these reactions appear to proceed step by step as shown below.

depending upon the activating influences of other groups; and (v) the formation of trisulphides is readily accounted for, on the basis of the equation (a).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Naphthalene Dithiochloride.—To a solution of naphthalene (10 g.) in dry ether, sulphur monochloride (6 c. c.) was added, using bismuth chloride (0.2 g.) as a catalyst. The reaction mixture was kept aside for a day.

On removal of the ether a plastic mass was obtained which was washed successively with hot methyl alcohol, hot ethyl alcohol, and finally with ether. Thus a granular compound was obtained which was then treated with carbon tetrachloride in a Soxhlet for further purification, m.p. 156° , yield 6.5 g. Sulphur dichloride gave identical product, but the yield was 1 g. only. (Found : Cl, 15.8 ; S, 28.4. $C_{10}H_7ClS_2$ requires Cl, 15.7 ; S, 28.3 per cent).

To 2 g. of the above compound, 15 c.c of concentrated nitric acid were added. The reaction was completed by warming. On cooling, the reaction mixture was poured over ice-water. A yellow compound separated, which melted at 58° (alcohol). Its mixed melting point with an authentic sample of α -nitronaphthalene showed no depression.

Anthracene Dithiochloride.—To a suspension of anthracene (5 g.) in petroleum, sulphur monochloride (6 g.) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for a few minutes, when a reddish solution was formed. On cooling, a solid separated which was removed by filtration, and crystallised from benzene, m. p. 212° . (Found : Cl, 12.7 ; S, 23.3. $C_{14}H_8ClS_2$ requires Cl, 12.84 ; S, 23.15 per cent).

Anthracene Tetrathiodichloride.—To a suspension of anthracene (10 g.) in dry ether, sulphur monochloride (10 c.c.) was added, using aluminium mercury couple as catalyst (*cf. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 887). The reaction mixture was kept overnight, and next day the ether was removed by distillation. The residue was washed with hot alcohol and hot benzene to remove the unacted anthracene. Finally the product was treated with carbon tetrachloride in a Soxhlet, m.p. 257° , yield 7.5 g. It was also obtained when sulphur dichloride was used instead of sulphur monochloride. (Found : Cl, 19.0 ; S, 34.4. $C_{14}H_8Cl_2S_4$ requires Cl, 18.9 ; S, 34.1 per cent).

The above compound on oxidation with chromic acid in glacial acetic acid in the usual way gave anthraquinone.

4 : 4'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl Disulphide.—To a solution of α -naphthol (10 g.) in dry ether, sulphur monochloride (5 g.) was gradually added when there was a visible reaction with a distinct change in colour of the reaction mixture. Next day the reaction mixture was rapidly filtered, and ether was removed by distillation. The residual viscous mass was treated with glacial acetic acid, and filtered. The filtrate was diluted with water and left overnight. The solid mass now formed was taken up with the least quantity of ether, methyl alcohol added and scratched when a colourless solid separated out. It was filtered, and very rapidly washed with small quantities of methyl alcohol, yield 2 g. It was then crystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 212° . (Found : S, 18.3. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires S, 18.28 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative of the above compound was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 172°. (Found: S, 7.8. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4S$ requires, S, 7.9 per cent). This shows that during acetylation one sulphur atom is eliminated.

4:4'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl disulphide (4 g.) was taken in ether and treated with 2 c.c. of sulphuryl chloride. The excess of the reagent and the ether were removed by distillation. The residue was very rapidly washed with small quantities of ether, and then crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 116-17°. (Acetyl derivative, m.p. 44°). It was identical with 4-chloro- α -naphthol (Ber., 1893, 26 3052), prepared by treating α -naphthol with sulphuryl chloride.

Reaction of Sulphur Monochloride with α -Naphthylamine.— α -Naphthylamine (5 g.) was dissolved in carbon tetrachloride and sulphur monochloride (3 c.c.) was gradually added with constant shaking. A dark chocolate solid immediately separated. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, and then filtered, yield 8.5 g. It is insoluble in water, alcohol, and chloroform. Advantage was taken of this to rid it of other compounds of sulphur sticking to it, by treating with carbon tetrachloride in a Soxhlet. This washing was repeated till a constant m. p. 210-12° (decomp.) was obtained. It did not appear to be a primary amine and was unaffected by boiling with water or hot concentrated hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 4.5; Cl, 13.1; S, 35.4. $C_{10}H_7NClS_2$ requires N, 5.1; Cl, 13.1; S, 35.1 per cent).

On being refluxed with a solution of sodium hydroxide a green solid was obtained, m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 5.9; S, 40.4. $C_{10}H_7NS_2$ requires N, 5.9; S, 40.3 per cent).

α -Naphthylamine and sulphur dichloride also gave the same product, m.p. 210-12°.

Reaction of Sulphur Monochloride with β -Naphthylamine.— β -Naphthylamine was treated with sulphur monochloride in the same way as described above. The compound was red in colour, and melted at 115°. It was repeatedly washed with benzene and carbon tetrachloride. When it was treated with cold water, a green solid was obtained which contained no chlorine. It was crystallised from alcohol in golden flakes or yellowish red needles, m.p. 150° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.1; S, 40.5. $C_{10}H_7NS_2$ requires, N, 5.9; S, 40.3 per cent).

β -Naphthylamine treated with sulphur dichloride in similar manner gave the same compound.

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl Disulphide.—2-Acetyl- α -naphthol (10 g.) was dissolved in dry ether, and a small quantity of alcohol was added, using zinc chloride as a catalyst. Sulphur dichloride (5 c.c.) was then added and the reaction mixture kept aside. A solid separated out,

which was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185°. Its mixed melting point with 3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide (Airan and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was 170°. (Found: S, 14.9. $C_{24}H_{18}O_4S_2$ requires S, 14.7 per cent).

It gave an acetyl derivative identical with that of 3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide.

2:2'-Dihydroxydinaphthyl Trisulphide.—When β -naphthol (10 g.) dissolved in dry ether was treated either with sulphur dichloride or with sulphur monochloride (5 g.), 2:2'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide, m.p. 212° (Airan and Shah, *loc. cit.*) was obtained. After the removal of this sulphide from the reaction mixture the ether was removed from the filtrate by distillation, the residue was dissolved in alcohol, and methyl alcohol was added when a yellow solid separated out. Purified by crystallisation from alcohol, it melted at 118°. (Found: S, 25.1. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_3$ requires S, 25.01 per cent). It gave an acetyl derivative identical with that of 2:2'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide.

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